

ISic0228

I.Sicily inscription 0228

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

tuff

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico
Baldassare Romano, inventory 118

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Loc(us)

2. L(uci) Vecil[i] ·

3. Basili

4. dis v(ixit) · a(nnis) XII

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini and photograph

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175690

EDR 077925

EDCS 8900403

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1980.0525

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 153

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